

CONDITIONS AND FACTORS OF LOGISTICS INFRASTRUCTURE
DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *this article talks about the development of logistics infrastructure in the country, its current state, conditions and factors affecting it. The transport strategy should be an integral part of the country's industrial development strategy. However, despite the task of forming and maintaining the transport and economic balance of the country and planning the development of transport infrastructure based on it, such clear relations are not observed.*

Keywords. *Logistics, infrastructure, transport, factors, industry, economic balance, infrastructure.*

Comprehensive development of the country's transport system and production capacity requires the creation of a national industrial and logistics infrastructure. Based on practical experience, a systematic approach to solving this problem is proposed, taking into account the special role of railways.

The country's transport system is, by definition, the most important component of the industrial infrastructure. The transport strategy should be an integral part of the country's industrial development strategy. However, despite the task of forming and maintaining the transport and economic balance of the country and planning the development of transport infrastructure based on it, such clear relations are not observed.

Today, the share of industry in the gross domestic product of our country has increased by 1.5 times compared to the last decade, and the share of trade turnover

has increased by more than 3 times. The decrease in the volume of production was accompanied by structural changes in the economy: from a planned economy focused on domestic consumption to a market economy integrated into the world economic system. Local products were replaced by imported products, which in some cases threatened national security.

Uzbekistan is one of the countries with high logistics costs, which negatively affects the competitiveness of our country. The average value of the indicator of logistics costs is estimated as 11.5% of GDP in the world, and 19% in our Republic. It should be noted that the value of this indicator is often determined by objective factors: geographical location, climatic conditions, etc.

In such conditions, it is considered necessary to implement the priority directions of economic development, primarily to develop the transport system, and the state infrastructure. A clear definition of strategic directions requires an objective assessment of the current situation. The most complete assessment of the logistics industry in different countries of the world is reflected in the research of the World Bank.

The concept of creating terminal logistics centers, the need to modernize the terminal and warehouse complex of state railways is associated with a number of reasons, the main of which are the decrease in cargo turnover, non-compliance with market requirements for the range and quality of services provided.

The dynamics of the structure of railway transport during the 30-year period of independence is characterized by a doubling of the share of raw materials, their dependence on the conditions of foreign markets and the lack of transport alternatives. Cargo owners are mainly large companies that are able to independently create infrastructure, purchase rolling stock and build logistics. The consumer of non-goods transportation services is medium and small business, whose competitiveness depends to a large extent on the efficiency of logistics solutions.

The railway monopoly could not quickly respond to changes in the market

conditions and caused a significant part of non-primary goods to "get stuck" in vehicles, therefore, the urgent task before the railways of Uzbekistan is, first of all, to the container. It is worth noting that the containerization rate in Asia and Europe, which is distributed in container transport, is about 140 TEU containers per 1000 people.

In Uzbekistan, the value of this indicator is approximately 20 TEU / 1000 people. In our reality, the container often serves as a factor that ensures cargo security and acts as a "warehouse", so the potential of containerization is higher. These conditions, as well as the development trends of the global and national markets of logistics services formed the basis of the concept of creating terminal and logistics centers (TLM) in the territory of our country (hereinafter the Concept). In 2019, the Ministry of Transport of Uzbekistan adopted a decision on the establishment of terminal and logistic centers.

The concept of creating a terminal logistics center was sent to the Ministry of Transport, the Ministry of Regional Development, the State Customs Service, the SCO with a proposal to create an interdepartmental working group for its implementation. However, the idea of such an interaction was not supported. Industrial and logistics infrastructure. It was considered that a new approach to the development of the national transport system should be based, first of all, on the planned parameters of the strategy for the comprehensive development of industrial and logistics capacities.

Let's define the concept of industrial and logistics infrastructure (SL), in particular, it is formed to provide benefits to local producers due to the reduction of logistics costs. It is a system created according to the topology, technical requirements, technological standards, etc. defined by the relevant regulatory authorities.

In addition, it is expected to achieve multiplicative, synergistic and other systemic effects. The creation of industrial capacities together with high-quality logistics services ensures the competitiveness of the manufacturer. As a result,

production volumes are increasing, high financial results and necessary social effects are being achieved. OR is formed in advance, which allows to optimize capital and operating costs for resource provision, transportation services, and avoid latifundistic manifestations.

Taking into account the specificity of general transport tasks and the practice of investment activities in the Republic, it is appropriate to talk about the superiority of the state in the management of the Project in the initial stages in order to coordinate the actions of the project participants. It is preferable that issues such as land relations, connection to transport infrastructure, connection to engineering networks, implementation of a uniform technical policy in design work and organization of operator activities, licensing procedures, and implementation of state support measures are implemented by the state. .

Implementation of these approaches should be provided with systematic solutions. One of the most important decisions is to give the status of strategic importance for the state (such as walls of walls, airport runways, military platforms, etc.) to individual elements of the OR (in particular, the status of a piggyback terminal). object of mobilization, which includes adaptation of the normative and legal framework.

The overall plan for the development of the national OR (including public transport infrastructure, network profile, deployment topology in relation to resources, etc.) should also become a systemic solution approved by the regulator. The topology of industrial logistics parks is based on TLM concept solutions.

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